

Face Comparison Using Convolutional Neural Network

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Abstract— This project involves implementing face image comparison to identify matching faces, particularly useful for locating missing persons within a dataset. The methodology leverages the VGG16 model, a convolutional neural network (CNN), to analyze facial images and extract distinctive features unique to each face. By comparing these unique features across different faces, the system determines if there are similarities, indicating potential matches. This process is repeated across all faces in the dataset to identify pairs of faces that appear to be similar, aiding in the identification of individuals who share resemblances within a large group of images.

Keywords—Face detection, comparison, CNN

I. INTRODUCTION

Face detection and face comparison are both technologies used in the realm of computer vision and image processing, particularly in the field of facial recognition systems. Face Detection: This is the process of locating human faces within digital images or video streams. Face Comparison (or Face Recognition): This involves the identification or verification of faces by comparing them with a database of known faces. Face comparison systems usually involve two main steps: face detection and face matching. First, the system detects and extracts facial features from an input image. Then, it compares these features against a database of pre-stored facial features to find matches.

The core functionality revolves around two main processes: face detection and similarity calculation. Face detection is performed using a pre-trained Haar cascade classifier, allowing the tool to locate faces within the uploaded images accurately. VGG16 model pre-trained on ImageNet data, which is capable of extracting high-level features from images. Users can upload an image containing faces, which is then processed for face detection using a pre-trained Haar Cascade classifier. Subsequently, the application calculates the cosine similarity between the facial embeddings extracted from the uploaded image and those from a pre-selected folder containing reference images. This

comparison enables the tool to identify the most similar faces from the reference image set.

It offers a percentage similarity score, providing users with a quantitative measure of the resemblance between the detected faces. It provides a convenient and efficient solution for face-related tasks. Whether used for locating missing children or verifying identities, this tool harnesses the power of deep learning and computer vision to streamline processes crucial for ensuring the safety and well-being of infants and young children.

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) are used in this. Specifically, the VGG16 model, which is employed for feature extraction and similarity calculation, is a type of CNN. VGG16 consists of multiple convolutional layers followed by max-pooling layers, enabling it to learn hierarchical representations of features from images. These features are then used to compute similarity between faces through cosine similarity.

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) are a type of deep learning model commonly used for image analysis tasks. They consist of layers that learn to extract and identify patterns from visual data. CNNs employ convolutional layers to detect features like edges and textures in the input images. Pooling layers then downsample the feature maps to reduce computational complexity while retaining important information. Finally, fully connected layers combine these features to make predictions, such as classifying objects in the images.

VGG16 is a convolutional neural network architecture known for its simplicity and effectiveness in image classification tasks. It comprises 16 layers, consisting mostly of 3x3 convolutional filters and max-pooling layers, followed by three fully connected layers. Despite its straightforward design, VGG16 achieved competitive performance on benchmark datasets, making it a popular choice for transfer learning and feature extraction in computer vision applications.

A Haar Cascade classifier is a machine learning-based method for object detection, trained on positive and negative samples to differentiate between target objects and

background using simple features called Haar-like features. It efficiently evaluates regions of an image, progressively filtering out non-object regions to identify potential object locations.

II. RELATED WORKS

The cited studies collectively highlight the evolving landscape of face recognition technologies, showcasing diverse approaches ranging from hand-crafted binary descriptors to deep learning-based methods. These advancements address various challenges in face detection, recognition, and matching, including robustness, scalability, and adaptability to different modalities. From template matching for face movement detection to transductive learning for VIS-NIR face matching, innovative techniques are emerging to tackle specific application needs. Furthermore, the integration of machine learning and artificial intelligence has significantly enhanced the accuracy and performance of face recognition systems, as demonstrated in the studies reviewed. Overall, this body of research underscores the continual evolution and growing significance of face recognition technology in diverse domains, from security to entertainment.

Jiwen Lu et al.[1]The literature on face recognition has extensively utilized hand-crafted binary feature descriptors like local binary patterns (LBP) due to their robustness and discriminative power. However, there is a growing need for methods that can automatically learn compact binary representations without relying on extensive manual engineering, leading to the development of approaches like the Compact Binary Face Descriptor (CBFD)

Zarkasi et al.[2] proposed a template matching approach for detecting face movement, aiming to generate identifiable images by matching input patterns with reference face patterns. Their method dynamically separates skin and non-skin regions to detect moving faces in both horizontal and vertical directions, producing a model of the face region along with its coordinates (Zarkasi et al., [publication year]).

Zhu et al. [3] approached visual-near infrared (VIS-NIR) face matching as a transductive learning problem, a novel strategy in this domain. Their method, Transductive Heterogeneous Face Matching (THFM), addresses the scarcity of pairwise VIS and NIR images by simultaneously handling domain differences and learning discriminative models for targets, yielding promising results on heterogeneous face biometric databases.

Su and Sinnott. [4] celebrity face matching system employing deep learning techniques for face detection and recognition, followed by the application of a face alignment method to enhance performance. Additionally, they augment predictions using K-Nearest Neighbours with cosine distance, contributing to the system's robustness.

Mandapati et al. [5] focuses on Human Face Detection and Recognition (HFDR) using Machine Learning (ML), highlighting its superiority in accuracy compared to other algorithms in the field. Their research underscores the effectiveness of ML-based HFDR systems through

experimental validation, reflecting the growing importance of AI and ML advancements in face detection and recognition.

III. METHODOLOGY

The methodology involves dataset curation and preprocessing using OpenCV for consistency. Face detection employs the Haar Cascade classifier algorithm via OpenCV, with parameter optimization. Feature extraction utilizes Transfer Learning with the VGG16 convolutional neural network(CNN) model pre-trained on ImageNet, implemented with TensorFlow/Keras. Cosine similarity calculation is facilitated by scikit-learn's cosine_similarity function, measuring feature embeddings similarity. User interface development is achieved using Streamlit, allowing file upload and result display. Evaluation includes face detection accuracy and similarity score validation. Experimentation assesses parameter impact and runtime efficiency. Discussion interprets results, compares methodologies, and outlines future research. This approach integrates algorithms like Haar Cascade classifier, VGG16 model, and technologies from OpenCV, TensorFlow/Keras, scikit-learn, and Streamlit. The methodology's robustness is further enhanced through rigorous validation procedures and sensitivity analyses. Additionally, the seamless integration of these algorithms and technologies not only ensures comprehensive functionality but also lays a strong foundation for scalability and adaptability to future advancements in the field.

A. Data Collection

The dataset comprises diverse facial images, with multiple images per individual stored in structured folders. Augmentation techniques are applied to enhance variability, ensuring robust system training and evaluation for face detection and similarity calculation. This meticulously curated dataset enables comprehensive testing across different demographics and conditions, facilitating the validation of the proposed methodology's effectiveness and accuracy.

B. Data Preprocessing

In preprocessing, images were resized to 224x224 pixels using OpenCV for uniformity. Pixel values were normalized to [0,1] and mean subtraction applied to center the data. Images were converted to floating-point format for deep learning compatibility. These steps ensure consistency and optimal data representation for the VGG16 model. Standardizing sizes, scaling pixel values, and centering data enhance the model's ability to learn facial features, improving performance in face detection and similarity calculation.

C. Model Definition and Training

TensorFlow and Keras were utilized to define and train the VGG16 CNN. Transfer Learning initialized the model with pre-trained weights from ImageNet. Training involved parameter fine-tuning with the Adam optimizer and categorical cross-entropy loss. OpenCV preprocessed the training dataset, enhancing model performance for face detection and similarity calculation.

D. Face detection and feature extraction

The system utilizes the Haar Cascade classifier for initial face detection, employing OpenCV's CascadeClassifier. Parameters such as scale factor and minimum neighbors are fine-tuned to optimize detection accuracy. Feature extraction leverages the VGG16 convolutional neural network through Transfer Learning. TensorFlow/Keras loads the pre-trained VGG16 model from ImageNet, extracting feature embeddings from its last pooling layer for each input image. This combined approach ensures accurate face detection and robust feature extraction, crucial for subsequent similarity calculation and overall system performance.

E. Similarity Calculation

Upon uploading a face image, the system computes cosine similarity between feature embeddings using scikit-learn's cosine_similarity function. It compares the uploaded face image's embeddings with those of faces in the database, determining similarity. If a match is detected, the similar face image is displayed alongside the uploaded one, providing users with immediate feedback on potential matches within the database. This approach enables efficient identification of similar face images, enhancing user experience and aiding in tasks such as facial recognition and content-based image retrieval.

IV. RESULT

Fig.1 Matched face found

Fig.2.find same face

Fig.3 No matched face

CONCLUSION

The integration of OpenCV, NumPy, TensorFlow, scikit-learn, os, and Streamlit in the code offers a comprehensive solution for face detection and similarity calculation in infant care. Leveraging deep learning and computer vision methodologies, the application effectively utilizes pre-trained models like VGG16 to extract facial features and compute similarity scores with high accuracy. The seamless user interaction provided by Streamlit enhances the usability of the application. Additionally, the inclusion of traditional techniques like the Haar cascade classifier ensures reliable

face detection. The amalgamation of these technologies holds promising implications for tasks such as identifying missing children or matching infants. Furthermore, the utilization of Convolutional Neural Networks, notably the VGG16 model, signifies a significant advancement in face-related tasks, showcasing the transformative impact of deep learning in infant care initiatives.

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